

Message from the Editor

Our actions are deeply influenced by the way we think about things. Our conceptual orientation affects almost all decisions and areas of our lives. Concepts pervade our lives. They influence our interpretation of social and personal experiences and the decisions we make in response. This is also true for school settings. Schools are surrounded by countless planned and unplanned situations and experiences that influence their mental health and well-being. Therefore, how teachers, parents, and school administration conceptualise a certain idea often directly influences the students' lived experiences of the same.

For instance, if a teacher believes discipline to be the same as controlled student behaviour, it will have visible implications for the teacher's treatment of the student, especially in cases of indiscipline. The teacher is likelier to keep strict rules and harsh punishments when those rules are broken. Micromanagement would be yet another trait the teacher may display. Similarly, if a teacher conceptualises learning as behaviour modification, most of her focus would be on students' exam performance. Consequently, her pedagogy may revolve around strategies that help students score better grades and, in the process, overlook other aspects and goals of schooling and education. However, we are often unaware of this underlying conceptualisation as one of the reasons for this failure in achieving our educational and curricular goals.

In such a scenario, our remedial measures also do not focus or consider reflecting on our conceptual understanding of ideas, leading to confusion and frustration. While the conceptual base is not all there is to any emergent issue at hand, it undoubtedly is the foundation of the experiences one may undergo in a certain situation. Therefore, carefully reflecting on how we understand a certain concept may bring mental clarity and help us refine our practices, leading to more meaningful experiences. Rather, it is necessary to reflect on the concepts involved to ensure that the school ethos and the educational processes taking place in the school are fulfilling their intended aims.

The authors have identified certain concepts that influence school children's mental health and well-being in the current issue of the Journal for School Mental Health and Well-Being. The volume begins with Ms. Nita's reflection and attempts to understand silence and its varied manifestations that one may get to observe and experience, especially in classroom settings. She argues that silence, as often desirable and expected from school students, may not always be productive. Silence can reflect oppression and a hegemonic power structure that needs intervention. The article questions the image of a silent student as a disciplined student and urges everyone to inquire and identify the underlying causes that may promote a culture of silence in schools. It also demands the reader to reflect on the implications such varied conceptions of silence may have upon the various educative processes undergoing in school and how being able to voice one's opinion could be a privilege.

Further, Ms. Ankita's writing explores the ideas of privilege, merit, rewards, and their relationship with each other. The paper simultaneously explores the impact of their conception and the nature of their relationship can have on one's very existence in society. Privilege not only influences one's way of being in society but also one's experience and performance in school. While it may be seemingly harmless to reward meritorious performances, it could also be a drastic overlooking of the struggles of the other students who put in equal hard work, but their lack of privilege pushed them down in the merit. Rewarding meritorious students raises questions about our understanding of assessment and inclusion. We aim and claim to be inclusive in our practices but serve each student a standard assessment to appear while completely overlooking their differences, including the privilege of some.

The following paper by Ms. Swati demands that readers acknowledge one's privilege and argues for the value of prayer in school with the hope of developing humility among students and teachers. The article responds to one of the most popular critiques of holding a morning prayer in schools: it makes students abandon all power and accountability and renders them ignorant. It urges us to reimagine prayer as an acknowledgement of our privileges, fortunes and fateful circumstances that we have no control over, such as those dictated by birth. Prayer, conceptualised as an act of expressing gratitude rather than an act of surrender, may broaden the horizons of students' imagination beyond their selves.

Moving on, Ms. Manisha urges us to think about developing critical thinking among students while comparing and contrasting the same with the idea of independent thinking. She argues how schools, in the name of developing critical and creative thinking, push children to think alike and, in the process,

repress their independent thinking. Children are pushed to think the way the adults, i.e., teachers, administrators, parents, policymakers and other stakeholders want them to think. It defeats the educational goal of developing thinking individuals who exhibit a critical outlook and can make informed decisions.

After that, Ms. Shikha argues for the need to reflect upon the development of morality among school children. Children's moral development has also been emphasised in NEP 2020 as it has implications for developing a good citizen and human being. She then suggests tools and methods such as discussion, dialogues, philosophy for children (P4C), and discussing moral dilemmas to help children deal with moral issues and make informed choices.

Often, our decisions and choices are influenced by the company we keep. Mr. Parikshit's article brings up the idea of friendship and how the implications of the same cut across various goals and aims any educational process may envision. Friendships between students may hold valuable pedagogic insights that teachers may benefit from. Friendships are not just personal relationships devoid of educational value but an extension of students' being that requires due consideration, especially within the caveat of wholistic education. The article argues that we must care about seemingly inconsequential and unrelated aspects of students' lives, such as friendships.

Subsequently, Ms. Garima's paper enquires into the students' and teachers' perceptions of care. It tries to gauge who students perceive as a caring teacher and compare the same with what attributes teachers associate with the idea of a caring teacher. The paper moves on to identify the gaps between the perceptions of the two groups and examine the effects they may cause while simultaneously reflecting on how the gap between the two can be permeated. Caring cannot be restricted to behaviours and attitudes within the classroom but needs to extend to outside activities and instances. A teacher needs to become a caring teacher, often by taking a break from engaging with students in a strictly professional fashion, but consider acting in a manner that allows the student to feel cared for.

Ms. Achint Kaur touches on another highly frowned upon and undervalued idea in any academic space: taking a break. While the phrase is commonly and casually tossed around to professionals, its boundaries remain untouched in schools, especially in the term's true meaning. School life is considered a life full of breaks (vacations) now and then. However, each break is an opportunity to catch up with pending tasks or get a head start on upcoming ones. It is more than visible in practices such as holiday homework for students and stay-backs for teachers. These practices reflect a flawed conception of breaks, and a severely undermined value of the role taking a break has in one's life, be it as a child or adult. It points towards the need for us to rethink the aim and intent of taking a break and when and how we take one.

The final paper in the volume is a step ahead in the direction and looks into the possibilities that music may offer in the lives of students and teachers. It proposes Indian folk music as a potential learning opportunity for music and incorporating cultural diversity, advancing language development and building a more inclusive atmosphere. It surveys various dimensions of music and comments upon society's perception of music as only a leisurely pursuit. While music is a highly aesthetic experience, it comes with a list of advantages and possibilities it merits for teachers, students and human beings.

While these concepts seriously affect the school systems, the list continues. How we understand and conceptualise an idea transcends into our attitude and practice. Therefore, it becomes important that we think about these ideas to be more reflective and informed in our practices in life. I humbly present to the readers this volume of the Indian Journal of School Health and Well-being, hoping that it will become a beginning point for all to reflect upon ideas and experiences of daily life and render them more meaningful.

Dr. Vikas Baniwal
Assistant Professor
Department of Education
University of Delhi